

DIMENSIONS OF EDUCATION

An International Journal of Education and Research -English Quarterly

Imagine without Girl

**Women,
Education
and
Empowerment**

**Economic
Rights and
Empowerment
of women**

Dimensions of Education

An International Journal of Education and Research English - Quarterly

7th June 2021

Vol. : 11

Issue : 1

Publisher

Jayadev M. Menasagi

Vidyanidhi Prakashana, Gadag.

Former Syndicate Member Karnataka University, Dharwad.

Editor

Dr. S.B. Yadawad

Co-Editor

Dr. Prakash K. Badiger

Editorial Board

Prof. M. S. Talawar

Professor (Rtd.), Dept. of Education,
Bangalore University, Bangalore.

Prof. Surekha Ksheerasagar

Professor, Dept. of Education,
Gulbarga University, Kalaburgi.

Prof. Asheesh Srivastava

Dean, School of Education,
Mahatma Gandhi Central University, Bihar.

Prof. Mushtaq Ahmad I. Patel

Professor Dept. of Education & Training, MANNU and
Registrar, Central University of Karnataka, Kalaburgi.

Prof. B. L. Lakkannavar

Akkamahadevi Women's University, Vijayapur and
Registrar, K.S.R.D.P.R. University, Gadag.

Dr. Madhusudan J.V.

Associate Professor, Dept. of Education & Education
Technology, School of Social Science,
University of Hyderabad.

Dr. Shashikant D. H.

Faculty & Placement Officer,
Karnataka State Rural Development and
Panchayat Raj University, Gadag.

Dimensions of Education

An International Journal of Education and Research - Quarterly

Vidyanidhi Prakashana®
Sri Sivakumar Agency®

Station Road, and 'Nanasu' J.T.Matha Road,
GADAG-582 101 Dist. : Gadag.

Karnataka State (India) Phone : 08372-237527, 277527

email : dimensionsofedn@gmail.com

www.vidyanidhionline.com

The views expressed in the articles in side are the individual opinions of the authors and they in no way represent or reflect the opinion of DIMENSIONS OF EDUCATION nor does DIMENSIONS OF EDUCATION subscribe to these views in any way. All disputes are subject to the jurisdiction of Gadag court only.

Dimensions of Education

INSIDE

Articles

05 Channels of Communication

- Dr. G.B. Devamma, Dr. Girija

07 Financial Impact of COVID-19

- Dr. Girija, Dr. G.B. Devamma

08 Imagine without Girl !

- Dr. Laxmidevi Y.

09 National Education Policy-2020 Quality of Higher Education in India

- Dr. Ravi C.S.

12 Why Online Teaching is Important?- Amreenaz Shaikh

14 Serviceability of Sundalli Nagaraju in the Prosperity of Depressed classes and His Gramasindhu Magazine

- Dr. K. Guruswamy

Research

18 The Effect of Students Curiosity and Imagination on overall Classroom Achievements

- Prof. S.M. Rajashekar, Dr. Rajashekar N.

23 Economic Rights and Empowerment of Women

- Prof. Panchalingappa B. Kanavi

27 A Relationship of Selected Anthropometrical Variables to Performance of Kabaddi Players

- Manjunath Mannur, Dr. B. M. Patil

31 An Interaction Effect of Teaching Competency with Locus control of location, Gender and Qualification of Primary School Teachers

- Dr. Nagaraj M. Shivalli

36 Women, Education and Empowerment

- Dr. Yerriswamy E.

41 A Study on the Effectiveness of Home Based Education Programme for the Severely disabled Children in Channarayapattana Taluk

- Dr. Chidananda A. L.

45 The Economic Impact of Pandemic in the Rural Area: with special Reference to Women's in North Karnataka

- Dr. Suresh K. P.

Thinkers on Education

49 John Locke

- J. M. Menasagi